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School Libraries in India: Present-day Scenario

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School Libraries in India: Present-day Scenario

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Panjab University

Chandigarh, India

Introduction

The education system in India is based on the British system of education. The Government of India lays stress on education for all. The directive principle contained in article 45 states that the state has to provide free and compulsory education for all until the age of 14 years. According to 2001 census, 65% Indians are literate and almost every child has an access to school with around 95% of our rural education having a primary school within one kilometer of their habitation. The school education in India is at three levels-Primary (classes 1 to 5), Middle (classes 6 to 8) and Higher/Secondary (classes 9 to 12). There are two categories of schools-government schools that are entirely funded by the government and others being the public (private) schools. There are about 888 thousands educational institutions in the country with an enrollment of about 179 millions. Elementary education system in India is the second largest in the world with 149.4 millions children enrolled in the age-group of 6 to 14 years. All the states and Union Territories of India have adopted a uniform structure of school education, i.e., the 10+2 system of education. Higher education is provided by 237 universities, which include 34 agricultural universities, 15 medical institutions, 39 deemed to be universities and 11 institutions of national importance and 8 open universities in addition to 10600 colleges. Education in India is primarily the responsibility of the state governments although the central government also plays an important role in higher education. Though education is in the concurrent list of the constitution, the state governments play a major role in the development of education particularly in the primary and secondary education. Para 11.4 of NPE 1986 states that the investment on education be gradually increased to reach a level of 6% of the national income as early as possible. In spite of the resource constraints, the budgetary allocation on education has increased over the years. As part of the mid-term Strategic Plan and the Millennium Development Goals priorities, UNICEF India is also committed to ensuring quality education for all children.

Role of School Libraries

School is a gateway to knowledge and plays an important role in building up a love for reading. The school library is integral to this educational process. Encouraged at the right age, the children are sure to develop a love for books. "Catch 'em Young" is therefore the motto of the school libraries. According to IFLA/UNESCO School Library Manifesto, "the school library provides information and ideas that are fundamental to functioning successfully in today's information and knowledge-based society. The school library equips students with life-long learning skills and develops the imagination enabling them to live as responsible citizens". It plays this role by selecting, acquiring and providing access to appropriate sources of information. The school library offers books and other resources ranging from print to electronic media for completion of various school projects and assignments, for acquisition of knowledge about a topic taught in class, for finding information about a hobby or current events and news, etc. The school librarian helps the students in finding the books/information on the topics of their interest. The librarians along with the teachers work together to achieve higher levels of literacy. While highlighting the role of the school library as the heart of school, Dr. Ranganathan stated that the school libraries should

act as laboratories for students and the librarians should function as guides to help the students in learning and using the books for improvement of knowledge and scholarship.

Standards for School Libraries

The school library is essential for literacy, education and information provision as well as for economic, social and cultural development of a nation. Hence, the school libraries must have adequate and sustained funding for trained staff, materials, technologies and facilities. As the responsibility of local, regional and national authorities, it must be supported by specific standards. Library standards are used to measure and evaluate the condition of the libraries as well as the degree of their development. They provide an outline for specific library activities and serve to define an ideal state of a library. The standards, which are developed professionally, indicate a direction for the libraries as to what tasks and objectives it should strive for. They provide school management with information on the management of libraries. Standards can have an international, national and regional scope. Internationally, standards are not only developed by the library organizations, such as IASL (International Association of School Libraries) and IFLA, but also by UNESCO or ISO. Keeping in view the vital role a school library plays in supporting the curriculum, such organizations have issued a School Library Manifesto whose 1998 version became a known text and is used by the school librarians all around the world. The manifesto indicates the role of school library, its mission and the most important tasks as well as the exceptional importance of a qualified school librarian. 'School Librarians: Guidelines for Competency Requirements' was published in the series- IFLA Profound Reports as number 41 in August 1995. The Library Association (CILIP) has also published a completely revised edition of the guidelines for 'school libraries in secondary schools' in 2002. These standards usually describe the staff requirements, acquisitions of collections, audiovisual and computer equipment as well as budgetary calculations.

School Libraries in the Current Environment

The school library is an essential partner in the local, regional and national library and information network. The school librarian has to be professionally qualified because he is responsible for planning and managing the library. Supported by the teachers, he not only inculcates love for reading amongst the future citizens of the country but also helps in information literacy. The role of school librarian as a teacher is to analyze the information needs of his clients for which he seeks help from the teachers. . He must have good interpersonal skills and should be able to take on the decisional roles. The school librarian need to know what teachers like to work with and what information they need for teaching. Finally, the school librarian needs to know what is expected of the student and how and what are they being taught. In fact, the school librarians have to move away from the role of keeper of books to that of the information providers and support students in learning and using information regardless of its form and format. In an increasingly networked environment when the students at the school level are using IT skills for study, the school librarian must be competent in teaching different information handling skills both to teachers and the students. They help the teachers to use a broader range of teaching strategies and the students are helped in their project work, individual study, group research, reading and the teaching of ICT, etc. It has been observed that when the teachers and the school librarians work together, students achieve higher levels of literacy, reading, learning, problem solving and information and communication technology skills . It has also been noted that the students in schools with good school libraries learn more, get better grades, and score higher on standardized test scores than their peers in schools without the libraries.

School library professionals in the developed countries are now engaged in some exciting activities so as to remain effective in the midst of fast-moving technological changes. They are striving to provide smart researching methodologies and information literacy skill sets to students. They are using web 2.0 technologies including blogs to give updates on resources as well as to interact with users and host collaborative discussions, are connecting their readers by creating pages on social networking sites such as MySpace or Orkut, are offering RSS tools that allow users to subscribe to get new information as it goes online, are using wikis to get staff and students involved in creating online library-related resources, are using Podcasts and videocasts for the audio tours of the library , etc. As a result, school

libraries are now called "learning resource centres" and the school librarians as the 'learning resource centre managers'. Some of the examples of such services in school libraries are indicated below:

The screenshot shows a WordPress-style blog page for Livingston High School. The header includes the school's name, address, and phone/fax numbers, along with a 'HOME OF THE WOLVES' logo. The main content area features a post titled 'Ask Click and Clack by Tom and Ray Magliozzi' dated January 16, 2009. The post includes a book cover image and a review by Mr. Doyle. The right sidebar contains a calendar for January 2009, a search box, and category lists such as 'Book Review (179)', 'Biography (16)', 'Fantasy (14)', 'General Fiction (78)', 'Historical Fiction (23)', 'Mystery/Thriller/Horror (33)', 'Non-fiction (15)', 'Romance (17)', 'Science Fiction (22)', 'Sports (2)', and 'California Young Reader'.

<http://lhsblog.edublogs.org/> retrieved 22.1.09

Isinglass Teen Read Award Booktalks
Hopkinton High School & Hopkinton Middle School Library

| 297 Park Avenue | Contoocook, NH 03229 | 603 746 4167 | 603 746 5109 (fax) |

 | [Jump to the mp3s](#) | [Production Details](#) | [2005/2006](#) | [2006/2007](#) | [2007/2008](#) |

Welcome to our [Library's](#) fourth podcast series. We chose Isinglass booktalks because the [Isinglass Teen Read Award](#) is such a great project. It is real! Actual 7th & 8th graders (as opposed to their parents, teachers, or their librarians...) nominate the books, read the books, and choose the winner each year. Our hats are off to the [Barnston Public Library](#), Amy Inglis, and the teens who have spearheaded this effort since 2001.

If you like what you hear, [subscribe](#) via iTunes and have each episode delivered automatically. Or use the podcatcher of your choice with our RSS feed
<feed://www.hopkintonschools.org/hhs/library/podcasts/podcast.xml>

[Subscribe manually via iTunes.](#)

2008/2009 Isinglass Teen Read Award Nominees

Welcome to another year of the Isinglass booktalks!

 [Dark Water Rising](#), by [Marian Hale](#). Podcast published 9/30/2008.

 [Enter Three Witches](#), by [Caroline Cooney](#). Podcast published on 10/07/2008.

 [Drums, Girls, & Dangerous Pie](#), by [Jordan Sonnenblick](#). Podcast published on 10/14/08.

 [Runaway](#), by [Wendelin Van Draanen](#). Podcast published on 10/27/08.

 [Quantum Prophecy: The Awakening](#), by [Michael Carroll](#). Podcast published on 11/03/08.

start | SCHOOL LIBRARIE... | 2008-2009 Isingla... | 10:04 AM

<http://www.hopkintonschools.org/hhs/library/podcast2006.html> retrieved 22.1.09

Blossomwood Library Blog

HOME
BIRTHDAY BOOK CLUB
STUDENT BOOK REVIEWS

Get

Harry Potter and the Half Blood Prince

Harry Potter and the Half Blood Prince is one of the very best Harry Potter books ever. Harry is facing his most challenging year at Hogwarts (he won't be attending his 7th year of Hogwarts at Hogwarts). Another new Defence Against the Dark Arts professor at Hogwarts the fun loving Professor Slughorn He is an ok teacher but isn't that serious. Professor Dumbledore has to do something very dangerous involving Voldemort and Harry has to accompany him. Find out more and read the book! dc15

[Add comment](#) | [January 6, 2009](#)

Harry Potter and the Order of the Phoenix

Harry Potter and the Order of the Phoenix is a very adventurous book. It talks about Harry's fifth year at Hogwarts. Harry's summer with the Dursley's is always a big drag. Ron and Hermione aren't sending him letters back after he's sent a ton of them and there is a new Defence Against the Dark Arts teacher at Hogwarts, Professor Umbridge. She is the Minister of Magic's assistant and the Ministry doesn't believe that Voldemort is back even though Harry saw the evidence and is telling people the truth. That makes his friends turn back on him (not Ron and Hermione though) and Umbridge is giving Harry horrible detentions, almost expelling his favorite teachers, and won't give them proper lessons, so, Harry and the people who believe him start a Defence Against the Dark Arts club. The Order of the Phoenix collapses after a very, very dear person to Harry is murdered. Who is he? Find out more by reading the book! dc15

[Add comment](#) | [Tagged: Add new tag](#) | [December 9, 2008](#)

Jingle Bell Run..... Coming Soon!

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- [Announcements](#)
- [Biographies](#)
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- [Chapter Books](#)
- [Library Class Activities](#)
- [Nonfiction Books](#)
- [Student Book Reviews](#)

Links

- [Alabama Virtual Library](#)
- [Amazon.com Wish List](#)
- [AR Bookfinder](#)
- [Home Conned for Accelerated Reader \(AR\)](#)
- [Huntsville Public Library](#)

Calendar

January 2009

M	T	W	T	F	S	S
				1	2	3
4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	12	13	14	15	16	17
18	19	20	21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28	29	30	31

» Dec

Tags

Accelerated Reader

Add new tag

Adventure Animals

Atlanta Braves Baseball

Beach Day Book Fair desert

SCHOOL LIBRARIE...
Blossomwood Libr...

<http://blossomwoodlibrary.edublogs.org/> retrieved 22.1.09

home page discussion (3) history notify me

DECATUR HIGH SCHOOL LIBRARY Protected

Find Articles & Resources :: Find Books :: Test Practice :: Teacher Resources ::

ANNOUNCEMENTS
Check out our new inauguration '09 Pathfinders!

PATHFINDERS
Pathfinders are web pages designed to help you find information on a specific topic, most often an assignment given to you by your teacher.

College Research

- [College Resources](#)

English

- [Dehumanization Project](#)
- [Georgia Poets](#)
- [Literary Criticism](#)
- [Public Housing Project](#) - Ms. Bergman/Mr. Dominguez
- [Nota Bene](#) - Ms. Bergman's Home Page

Health P.E.

- [STDs](#)

Languages

Spanish

- [Arts](#)
- [Maya](#)

Multimedia

- [Images](#)

Science

- [Mr. DeWiese's Newton Book Project](#)
- [Ms. LeDoux's & Mr. Schan's 9th Grade Science Research](#)
- [Genetic Disorders](#)
- [Genetically Modified Foods](#)
- [Modern Medicine](#)

Senior Project Research Help

Library
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DHS Wiki Home
Decatur High School #
Find Articles & Resources
Find Books
Pathfinders
Library Blog #
Picturing America wiki

Other Educational Sites

Legend [What's this?]
G: GALILEO
DCPL: DeKalb County Public Library
CSD: City Schools of Decatur

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<http://dhs.wikispaces.com/> retrieved 22.1.09

teacherlibrarianwiki | FrontPage

Search wiki:

Home Edit page

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QuickStart Recent Activity SideBar

Create a new page
 Create a classroom
 Create a tabular
 Create a group project
 Use another template

Share this
 http://teacherlibrarianwiki.pbwiki.com/

Welcome to teacherlibrarianwiki!

Wikis are about collaboration; so are teacher-librarians! This is your wiki! (If you'd like to contribute, please write me at jovce_valencia@sdgt.org)

Let's use this space to SHARE our best wisdom and our best instruction—the new understandings, lessons, units, handouts, rubrics, presentations, images, and teaching tips that have been either rotting in our file cabinets or posted and lonely on our individual sites.

Let us demonstrate how teacher-librarians can use new landscapes to create serious professional tools.

I invite practitioners, library educators, and preservice librarians to contribute and help this space grow.

A couple of notes:
 If you add a page, please add it to the page list so folks can easily reach it. Add a page by enclosing the title of the page in **brackets** in the contents area below. Don't forget to also enter the addition on the Sidebar page.

Please respect copyright when adding materials to this wiki!

Contents

- [New: Saving school library programs for learners!](#)
- [Web 2.0 and School Library 2**](#)
- [*Tools for using wikis with students and faculty](#)
- [*Social Bookmarking](#)
- [*Links to our blogs](#)
- [*Links to our websites](#)
- [*Other library wikis](#)
- [*Open Source Resources for Education](#)
- [*Copyright Friendly Image Sources](#)
- Books**
- [*Must Have Graphic Novels Secondary](#)
- [*Must Have Graphic Novels Primary](#)
- [*Incredible books for elementary students](#)
- [*Booklists for elementary students](#)
- [*Incredible books for middle school students](#)
- [*Booklists for middle school students](#)

School Libraries in India

Although the college and university libraries have developed to a great extent as a result of the work done by UGC and INFLIBNET, the school libraries are a neglected lot in India. According to the 5th All India Educational Survey, only about 40% of the schools have libraries that too in public schools. Moreover, the situation in rural areas is worse than the urban areas. The number of the trained librarians working in the schools is still less. Although the central government has made libraries a priority to help raise the literacy rate, yet these are not receiving the right attention as revealed by the NCERT survey of 1993. Their resources in terms of staff and funds are scarce, as these have received the least priority. The school libraries neither have good collection nor sufficient space because of the financial constraints. Most of the schools have no qualified staff in their libraries. The libraries of public schools are slightly better as compared to their government counterparts. The situation is worst in case of libraries of

government primary and middle schools. As a result, the school libraries are neither able to inculcate the reading interests among the children nor do they help in achieving information literacy. The documents in most of the school libraries are kept in cabinets under lock and key and are made available to the students on demand only. A traditional card catalogue and Dewey Decimal system for classification of the documents is normally used. A majority of the school libraries have no computers in the libraries although a good number of them have set up the computer laboratories. The librarians select the documents in consultation with the teaching staff. The library acquires the magazines on current affairs and sports besides a number of daily newspapers in English, Hindi and other regional languages. The students of the primary classes have a library hour on the weekly basis when they are given storybooks so as to inculcate the reading habits. Majority of the school librarians in India do not provide any other service except the circulation of books in the absence of good library infrastructure. In 1998, the school library committee of the Indian Library Association surveyed the school libraries in Delhi and found that most of the government primary schools had no library at all and in secondary schools, the libraries were substandard. The report called for a fresh look at the way school libraries were organised. The committee also stressed that the library be made the hub of the school. Moreover, it was noted that the public (private) schools were better organised with better facilities like staff, collection and services as compared to the government schools. Such schools are continuously improving their collections and access to resources but the government schools suffer from lack of funds and staff. Majority of such schools does not even have a full time librarian and the teacher in-charge manages the library in the absence of the full time librarian. Although the number of school libraries in primary, secondary and the higher education is growing, yet there are many problems to overcome. The government has left the responsibility of school libraries to the school themselves for providing the resources and funds to establish well-equipped libraries. Most of the schools do not have a separate room for the library especially in government primary schools. Since the school authorities are not convinced about the appointment of professional staff for their libraries, they do not appoint professionally trained staff. Until a few years ago, only a few secondary schools had libraries with qualified library staff. Moreover, they are not paid well and as a result the well-trained librarians leave the school library whenever they get an opportunity to work elsewhere. Moreover, the status of school librarian is also low in India. Generally speaking, libraries in public schools are in a better position in terms of space, budget and staff than their counterparts in the government schools. Most of the public schools have appointed trained librarians and are computerized also.

Although, most of the public schools have their websites giving academic information, infrastructure available, etc, yet not much is available in the virtual space about their libraries and the services provided by them. In the current IT scenario, when the school libraries in the developed countries are being used as “school library media centers” with computer resources that enable children to access a wide variety of information, almost all of the school libraries are far from such a reality in India. The following screenshots of two popular schools clearly indicate the kind of services provided in their libraries:

KODAIKANAL INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL

The Place

- Introduction to KIS
- Principal's Welcome
- KIS Campuses
- KIS Facilities
 - Student
 - Staff
 - Libraries
 - Catering
 - Medical Care
 - Music
 - Visual & Performing Arts
 - Sport, PE & Leisure
 - Science & Technology
- KIS Tours
- KIS & Kodai Environs

The People

The Programs

The Process

Publications

Foundation

Features

Libraries at KIS

KIS has 3 libraries, one in each of the Elementary, Middle and High Schools. Each library is individually resourced and staffed by a librarian with experienced support staff.

All libraries at KIS are fully computerized with computers for displaying catalogue information, checking book availability as well as a bar code monitoring system to track circulation of library resources. Additional computers are supplied with internet access and CD-ROM use for student and community use.

KIS has a commitment to regular review of library materials and annual purchasing of new / replacement stock. Teaching staff, students and librarians are all involved in the selection of library resources. Purchasing is centralized with each individual KIS library deciding its budget allocation, expenditure and selection criteria.

In support of KIS as a boarding school with a full residential program, KIS librarians and staff provide flexible opening hours to respond to varied student needs. Librarians work closely with the Middle and High School academic staff and dorm parents to provide optimal student access to study and research facilities.

KIS libraries are spacious with over 350 square meters of combined space that generously allow for significant collections of age appropriate books, reference materials and periodicals.

KIS Library Program

KIS has a whole school library policy developed by the Head Librarian in consultation with KIS Senior Management Team and overseen by the Academic Vice Principal and the Ecotribun Leadership team comprising of Elementary, Middle, High School and IB Coordinators. Its aims are:

- To encourage and develop recreational reading
- To ensure that students and staff are effective and appropriate users of ideas and information
- To ensure that students are information literate information literacy is a key ability to accessing, evaluating and using information from a variety of sources

Library Curriculum Strands

- Reading / literature enjoyment and appreciation
- Information handling skills

Library Curriculum Rationale:

The need for a whole school library curriculum is based on the following premises:

Recreational reading:

- Students who read widely for pleasure gain both academically and developmentally. The direct benefits of developing reading habits are:
 - Improved reading comprehension
 - Improved use of written and spoken English and other languages
 - Growth in maturity through access to experiences beyond the reader's immediate world

Information society:

- We live and function in an information society
- Information is an infinite commodity and student needs for it are pervasive and essential
- Because technology changes the modes and pace for creating and storing information, it also demands changes in our information accessing strategies

<http://www.kis.in/place/facilities/libraries.html> retrieved 22.1.09

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VIRTUS ET LABOR

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DBL welcomes our alumnus Rav Shukla, the Amul Star Voice of India! We are proud to have you here in our midst!

Library

Strict silence and order must be observed by all. A student must have his library to enter the library. All article and personal belongings must be left outside when entering the library. Only a copy-book and library book, if to be returned, may be taken into the library. Only one book will be issued per card and no student can take a book on another's card. A book can be kept for one week only. No renewal will be allowed. Books exclusively for consultation are not to be taken out of the library. They remain available to all students. Before leaving the library every student must submit for scrutiny the books borrowed. All magazines, reference books used while in the library must be put back into the proper place. Books borrowed from the library must be returned personally to the librarian. They must not be circulated. A student who circulates books borrowed from the library may have his library card withdrawn and may be fined as well. If any defect is noticed in a book that is being borrowed, the librarian should be notified. Failure to do this checking renders one liable to be considered responsible for the defect noticed on the return of the book. Fines will be imposed for damages done to books and articles in the library. Books lost must be replaced by the borrower. A remark will be entered in the library page of the School Diary for every book returned late. Three such remarks will result in a general remark and a fine of Rs 50/- No fine will be charged for books overdue if a letter can be produced showing that the borrower has been absent for valid reasons Library cards are distributed once a year, in April. There are two cards: (a) Library Admit Card (b) Library Lending Card. Library Admit Card is to enter the library and Library Lending Card is to borrow a book. A lost card may be replaced by a new one, a fine of Rs.50/- following a request. No books may be retained during the summer, autumn and winter vacations. Library hours: Class days : 8.30 a.m. to 12 noon 1.00 p.m. to 3.30 p.m. Thursday : 8.00 a.m. to 12.00 noon During class hours (8.00 a.m. to 2.25 p.m.) only classes will be allowed into the library according to the time-table published by the Vice Principal. Permission to enter the library during these class-hours must be obtained from the Vice Principal. During other library hours no special permission is required provided a student has the Library Admit Card.

Current News

Pre-Board Examinations
The pre-Board Examinations will begin on 5th January 2009...
[read more...](#)

Swetank Jain R.I.P.
 We deeply mourn the sad and untimely demise of our alumnus Swetank Jain in a car accident in Kolkata on Saturday, 20 December 2008...
[read more...](#)

Mission Technothlon '08
"Hurrah" - with this the three of us leaped into the air when we received the e-mail confirming our participation in the Technothlon 2008 Mains, ...
[read more...](#)
[view more current news](#)

Current Events

Annual Prize Distribution
 Don Bosco School, Liluah celebrated their annual prize distribution ceremony on the 9th of May, 2008. The ceremony was held in the school auditorium. ...
[read more...](#)

May Day Celebrations
 Don Bosco School, Liluah celebrated May Day on the 2nd of May, 2008. The celebrations:

<http://www.dblh.org/display.php?page=school&pid=20> retrieved 22.1.09

Web 2.0 technologies all over the world are transforming the ways in which school libraries operate and deliver their services in this fast changing online social and collaborative world. However, only one school called ' Kendriya vidyalaya, Thiruvananthapuram' has a school library media centre. It uses web 2.0 technologies to a great extent and is providing ask-a-librarian service, blogging, etc.

Kendriya Vidyalaya Pattom
Thiruvananthapuram

- HOME
- CONTACT INFORMATION
- MISSION
- OUR VIDYALAYA
- LIBRARY
- RESULT ANALYSIS
- VMC/PTA MEMBERS
- ENROLMENT POSITION
- CATEGORY-WISE BREAKUP
- VACANCY POSITION
- STUDENT TRANSFER -I
- STUDENT TRANSFER II
- FACULTY FIRST SHIFT
- FACULTY 2ND SHIFT
- STAFF VACANCY
- PROJECT THINK.COM
- ICT INFRASTRUCTURE
- ADMISSION
- CURRENT NEWS
- STUDENT ACHIEVERS
- TEACHER ACHIEVERS
- SPORTS AND GAMES
- SCOUTS & GUIDES
- CCA - FIRST SHIFT
- CCA - SECOND SHIFT
- K.V UTSAV
- ALUMNI
- COMMITTEES
- PLACES OF INTEREST
- IMPORTANT LINKS
- BRIGHT PASS-OUTS
- OLYMPIADS/NTSE
- STREAMS
- FEE STRUCTURE
- CLASS TEACHERS SHIFT 1
- CLASS TEACHERS SHIFT 2
- SPECIAL PROGRAMMES
- HOLIDAYS
- NOTIFICATIONS
- CREATIVE CORNER

LIBRARY MEDIA CENTRE

The Library Media Centre

KVS adopted the New Library Policy as Article 137 and 138 in its Education Code in 2008.

The Library of the Vidyalaya has implemented a School Library Media Programme for the session 2008-'09, which was a full range of learning experiences arising out of school library assessment, resources, facilities, support services, technologies, community connections and staff leadership.

The library stock and services has automated to cope with the emerging needs of the students in the information age. The library merges new techniques and approaches along with the traditional routine functions.

For the complete information about the library media centre please log on to

LIBRARY MEDIA CENTRE

Home Works and Assignments Online

Dear students and parents,
You will get class wise homeworks and assignments here.

HOMEWORKS ONLINE (SHIFT-I)
HOMEWORKS ONLINE (SHIFT-II)

Library@Kendriya Vidyalaya Pattom

where things happen

HOME ANNOUNCEMENTS ANNUAL DAY 2008 VIDEOS ARUNDHATI ROY ASK THE LIBRARIAN BEST READER AWARDS 2008 CHILD HELPLINE CONTACT DDC FOR KIDS
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS DIRECTORY FREEDOM STRUGGLE GALLERY KARAN THAPAR INTERVIEWS KY WEB DIRECTORY LIBRARY CHARTER LIBRARY STATS LIBRARY TOUR
IN PHOTOS LITERARY VIDEOS MONTHLY REPORT (P & T) NATIONAL LIBRARY WEEK 2008 NEW ARRIVALS ONLINE CATALOGUE READER SERVICES REFERENCE RESOURCES SLMC
PROGRAMME 2008 USER STUDIES WELCOME WORLD BOOK DAY 2008 PRINCIPAL'S MESSAGE EMERGENCY LINES

Live updates

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January 15, 2009
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Republic Day Book Exhibition 23-26 January 2009

Sample Q papers, HOTS study materials, Question Banks

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You are the visitor number:

190,533

Dear Students,

It is your site use that will be your guide in information search. Ask questions in it that will mould your future. Discuss and tell about it, become a part of the universe of knowledge.

Recent updates

KVS Teacher Recruitment

Ask The Librarian

Who may use this service?

This service is available to the students, faculty, and staff of Kendriya Vidyalaya Pattom and any visitor to this site.

What does "Ask a Librarian?" service do?

It answers simple factual questions. Please submit your question using the mentioned online form. You will be contacted by the Librarian. Please describe your question in detail.

OR

mail to librerykvpattom@gmail.com

For additional assistance,

please visit the Library

38 Responses to "Ask The Librarian"

1. Sujita Aparajita said

April 3, 2009 at 10:05 am

may i plz know the name of 5th standard Environmental Studies textbook. And also i would like to know the name of its 1st lesson. thank you.

2. Soma Moitra said

April 26, 2009 at 1:01 pm

Dear Sir/Madam
I had completed my one year BLIS course, I had applied for Librarian Job in KVS School. My exam will be held on 21-06-2009. I need a book for my competitions examination. Please suggest me what type of question will come.

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Conclusion

A library is a storehouse of information and a key to the knowledge, but the era of information technology revolution has relegated the librarians especially in schools to the background. The audio-visual media specially the Internet has lured the budding readers away from the printed works like the Pied Piper. There is a great need for the upliftment of school libraries in India. If the reading habits of the students have to be changed, the conditions of the school libraries have to be improved. For this purpose, the central as well as the state government, the school authorities, the school librarian and the teachers will all have to work together.

Firstly, the government of India must ensure that the school library has a well-stocked active collection managed by a qualified librarian. For this purpose, a school library legislation should be passed as soon as possible

Secondly, the positive attitude of the school principal is very important. He should clearly lay down policies regarding the school library services including its goals, priorities and services as well as its relation to the school curriculum. In fact, CBSE has recently brought out a book entitled 'Organizing school libraries – Guidelines'. It provides useful information for the school principals to upgrade their school libraries and make them more functional. They should organise their school libraries according to the guidelines provided.

The school librarians in India must play a positive role of being the information providers. Librarians must assist the teachers and students to search out their information needs, critically evaluate the materials and use technological means to synthesize their findings into new knowledge. Hence, they must become proficient in the use of the new technologies themselves first to promote them and instruct students and teachers in their use. They must expand their traditional service environment to that of computer-based data and sophisticated information-seeking strategies. He must analyze their learning

and information needs, to locate and use resources and to communicate the same to their users. They must develop policies, practices, and curricula required by the students for information literacy. As such, they have to work closely with the teachers in planning and implementing learning programs that will equip students with the skills necessary to succeed in a constantly changing social and economic environment. They can also make use of the resources that are available on the Internet including 'Resources for School Librarians' (<http://www.sldirectory.com>) that indicates resources on learning and teaching, information access, program administration, technology, education and employment as well as continuing education, 'Advocacy toolkit' of AASL (http://www.ifla.org/V11/s11/pub/s11_AdvocacyKit.html) , International Children's Digital Library (<http://www.icdlbooks.org>) ,etc. The school librarian should also make a webpage of the school library highlighting the collection, OPAC and other services provided. Moreover, the school libraries in India should also become members of International Association of School Libraries and should send their details to it for inclusion of their name in the list of school libraries that is available online at http://www.iasl_slo.org/schoollibs.html

The library associations at the state as well as the national level can also play a very important role in the development of school libraries in India. Indian Library Association should support international initiatives to promote school library activities and should promote the importance of school libraries through their publications. These should support research in school librarianship and undertake projects to help school libraries to effectively perform the information literacy program . Such an agency should highlight the basic responsibilities of the school librarians as well as the responsibilities of the teachers and the school authorities towards the library by drafting standards keeping in mind the requirements of the present day school students. Regional workshops should also be conducted to promote best practices in the school libraries. However, in the absence of set standards, the school librarians in India can use IFLA/UNESCO school library guidelines for framing up various policies.

Indian School Library Association should be established on the pattern of other such associations the world over that should bring out a directory of school libraries, hold regular conferences for interaction amongst the school librarians and must bring out a journal featuring various aspects of school libraries.

Last but not the least, a network of school libraries can also be established.

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